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<p>Abstract: Baseline principles for ethical AI integration in democratic deliberation, addressing the 'AI penalty,' adversarial manipulation, and technocratic bias. Ten recommendations prioritise human-centered design, adversarial resilience, and EU-wide linguistic accessibility.</p>	
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Executive Summary

Target Audiences and Expected Outcomes

This policy brief addresses EU and national policymakers responsible for digital governance and democratic participation, as well as deliberation practitioners, including public administrators and platform operators. Secondary audiences include technology developers, civil society organisations and the wider research community.

Expected Outcomes:

- Inform investment decisions for AI-enabled deliberation infrastructure across the EU
- Establish baseline principles for ethical AI integration in democratic participation processes
- Provide actionable guidance aligned with evolving EU regulatory frameworks, including the AI Act and Digital Omnibus
- Address emerging risks of manipulation, polarization and adversarial exploitation in AI-enabled deliberation.

Key Recommendations

- **[HIGHEST PRIORITY]** Adopt human-centered design to build and sustain public trust while addressing the 'AI penalty'
- **[HIGH PRIORITY]** Design for "diabolical times": Build systems capable of actively countering polarization, bad-faith actors, and repairing democratic discourse
- **[HIGH PRIORITY]** Ensure linguistic accessibility with dedicated investment in AI infrastructure for all EU languages
- Invest in open, sovereign deliberation infrastructure with AI-ready text standards and transparent tools
- Establish AI deliberation security standards protecting against manipulation, adversarial attacks and coordinated inauthentic behavior

Regulatory Context

November 2025 Update: The European Commission's Digital Omnibus on AI proposes significant amendments to the EU AI Act, including extended compliance timelines for high-risk AI systems (now December 2027/August 2028), expanded regulatory sandboxes, simplified requirements for SMEs, and centralised AI Office oversight. These developments inform the recommendations in this brief. The proposals are subject to European Parliament and Council negotiation.

Evidence Base

This brief synthesises findings from 320+ academic papers reviewed in D1.1, analysis of 50 deliberation platforms and tools, identification of 23 distinct AI features mapped to

deliberation phases, internal stakeholder consultations across four pilot contexts (Greece, Italy, Germany, International), recent scholarship on deliberation under adversarial conditions (Bächtiger & Dryzek, 2024), empirical research on the 'AI penalty' in citizen engagement (Jungherr & Rauchfleisch, 2025) and practical infrastructure-building experience from GFOSSs glossAPI project for Greek language AI.

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Contents

Executive Summary	3
Target Audiences and Expected Outcomes	3
Key Recommendations.....	3
Regulatory Context.....	3
Evidence Base.....	3
1. The Challenge & Opportunity.....	10
1.1. The Scale-Quality Dilemma in Mass Deliberation.....	10
1.2. The AI Opportunity & Risk.....	10
1.3. Deliberation in 'Diabolical Times'.....	11
1.4. The Infrastructure Gap.....	11
1.5. EU Policy Alignment & Critique	12
2. Key Findings From Research	13
2.1. Conditions for Effective AI-Enabled Deliberation	13
2.1.1. Normative Conditions.....	13
2.1.2. Institutional Conditions.....	13
2.1.3. Technical Conditions.....	14
2.1.4. Legal and Ethical Prerequisites	14
2.2. Evidence from Platform Analysis: Capabilities and Limitations.....	15
2.3. Stakeholder Needs & The 'AI Penalty'	16
3. Policy Recommendations.....	17
3.1. For EU & National Policymakers.....	17
3.2. For Deliberation Practitioners.....	18
3.3. For Technology Developers	19
3.4. Addressing Critical Gaps	19
4. Looking Ahead.....	21
4.1. Empirical Validation Roadmap.....	21
4.2. Future Policy Briefs	21
GLOSSARY	22
REFERENCES	24

Acronyms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
DQI	Discourse Quality Index
DRI	Deliberative Reason Index
EDRI	European Digital Rights
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GenAI	Generative Artificial Intelligence
GPAI	General-Purpose Artificial Intelligence
LLM	Large Language Model
SME	Small and Medium-sized Enterprise
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines

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Partners List Abbreviations

Acronym/Abbreviation	Description
UNIS	UNI SYSTEMS SYSTMATA PLIROFORIKIS MONOPROSOPI ANONYMI EMPORIKI ETAIRIA - UNI SYSTEMS INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY SYSTEMS COMMERCIAL S.M.S.A.
TUD	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT - TU Delft
CERTH	ETHNIKO KENTRO EREVNAS KAI TECHNOLOGIKIS ANAPTYXIS - CENTRE FOR RESEARCH AND TECHNOLOGY HELLAS CERTH
UBAM	OTTO-FRIEDRICH-UNIVERSITAET BAMBERG - UNI BA
KT	KONNEKT ABLE TECHNOLOGIES LIMITED - Konnekt-able Technologies
UNIVDUN	UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE - UNIVDUN
IK	INŠTITUT ZA KRIMINOLOGIJO PRI PRAVNI FAKULTETI V LJUBLJANI - INSTITUTE OF CRIMINOLOGY AT THE FACULTY OF LAW LJUBLJANA
BRANE	Dembrane B.V. - Dembrane
TG	THOUGHTGRAPH LTD - TG
GFOSS	ETAIREIA ELEXYTHEROY LOGISMIKOY LOGISMIKOY ANOIKTOY KODIKA - GFOSS
AAIT	ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS - ACTIONAID INTERNATIONAL ITALIA ETS
CBAM	Stadt Bamberg - City of Bamberg
UZH	UNIVERSITY OF ZÜRICH

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List of Tables

Table 1. Stakeholder needs & concerns.....	16
Table 2. Glossary of terms.....	23

PENDING EC APPROVAL

1. The Challenge & Opportunity

1.1. The Scale-Quality Dilemma in Mass Deliberation

Democratic deliberation faces a fundamental tension. Meaningful participation requires depth, yet democratic legitimacy demands breadth. Traditional deliberative processes such as citizens' assemblies, town halls, public consultations, produce high-quality discourse but reach a limited number of participants. Digital platforms can scale participation to hundreds of thousands but often sacrifice deliberative quality for quantity.

Current digital deliberation faces persistent bottlenecks:

- **Moderation overload:** Human moderators cannot effectively process thousands of simultaneous contributions while maintaining quality standards
- **Information synthesis challenges:** Translating diverse citizen inputs into actionable policy insights remains labour-intensive and often incomplete
- **Accessibility, digital literacy, and linguistic barriers:** Multilingual deliberation, accessibility for users with disabilities, and varying levels of digital literacy require resources most platforms lack
- **Adversarial manipulation:** Coordinated inauthentic behavior and bad-faith participation undermine deliberative quality
- **The evaluation gap:** Limited systematic assessment of both deliberative quality and AI tool effectiveness creates uncertainty about what works

1.2. The AI Opportunity & Risk

Artificial intelligence offers potential solutions to these challenges. Our analysis identified 23 distinct AI features that can support deliberation across four process phases. These range from preparation tools (information provision, topic framing, fact-checking) through dialogue support (moderation assistance, real-time translation, accessibility enhancement) to synthesis capabilities (argument mining, comment clustering, consensus identification) and implementation aids (automated report generation, impact tracking).

However, AI-enabled deliberation confronts serious risks that demand equal attention:

- The 'AI penalty' as documented by Jungherr & Rauchfleisch (2025) finds citizens are less willing to engage in AI-facilitated deliberation and anticipate lower deliberative quality, creating a new 'deliberative divide' that may systematically exclude AI-skeptical populations.
- Manipulation at scale is another risk that needs to be taken early on into account. In 2017, a US regulatory proceeding on internet rules received 22 million public comments, but investigation revealed nearly 18 million (82%) were fraudulent. Broadband companies funded 8.5 million fake comments impersonating real citizens to influence policy. With generative AI, such campaigns can now produce 'limitless unique comments' evading the detection methods that identified the 2017 fraud (New York Attorney General, 2021; TechPolicy.Press, 2021).

- Minority voice suppression: Research demonstrates that LLMs risk underrepresenting minority perspectives and exhibit bias (Zhu et al., 2025)
- Power concentration: Private control over AI infrastructure enables concentrated corporate power to shape information flows in democratic processes
- Efficiency-legitimacy tension: Democratic legitimacy may require apparent 'inefficiency', that is time for reflection, minority voice amplification, considerations that AI optimization risks eliminating.

1.3. Deliberation in 'Diabolical Times'

Contemporary European democracy faces what Bächtiger & Dryzek (2024) term 'diabolical' challenges. Multi-dimensional threats featuring 'clever operators' who prosper by exploiting democratic pathologies. These operators deploy 'diabolic strategies' in the sense of spreading misinformation, extreme spin, and the imposition of their own reality through repetition without evidence.

AI-enabled deliberation in Europe is highly likely to function under conditions of **deep polarization, populism, extremism and denial** (Bächtiger & Dryzek, 2024, Chapters 4–7). This requires critical distinctions between populist citizens (with legitimate grievances) and populist elites (manipulative power-seekers); between exclusion of dangerous ideas and engagement with persuadable individuals; between requiring factual agreement and enabling productive dialogue across value divides.

Research on 'bridging rhetoric'—communication capable of reaching those who do not share the speaker's perspective—demonstrates deliberation can proceed productively without requiring agreement on contested facts. In climate deliberation forums, bridging rhetoric enabled participants to accept greenhouse gas mitigation measures even while continuing to dispute anthropogenic climate change, by focusing on shared values such as energy security and economic opportunity rather than contested scientific claims (Bächtiger & Dryzek, 2024, Chapter 6). AI deliberation systems shall be designed to support such nuanced engagement, not merely enforce consensus or exclude dissent.

1.4. The Infrastructure Gap

The promise of AI-enabled deliberation confronts a sobering reality. Europe lacks the open, AI-ready data infrastructure required for genuine digital sovereignty in this domain. Policy frameworks assume data availability but the everyday engineering reality shows otherwise. Experience building glossAPI¹, GFOSS's open infrastructure for Greek language AI, exposed how difficult it remains to produce AI-ready open data for European languages. Public documents exist in inconsistent formats across institutions. There are no standards for structuring administrative or legal text for AI training. Licensing for publicly accessible documents remains unclear. Every organisation must build its own preprocessing pipeline, duplicating effort across the EU.

Moreover, the current AI landscape presents 'open-washing' risks. Models release weights while hiding training data, claiming 'open source' status without meaningful transparency. For

¹ <https://glossapi.gr/?lang=en>

ethical AI-enabled deliberation, this matters because platforms may deploy models opaque about their training data and thus undermining the very transparency democratic processes require.

A critical insight emerges from comparing EU investment patterns. Millions flow to AI Factories for compute infrastructure, yet equivalent investment in open data pipelines, language-specific corpora and reproducible tools remains fragmented and inadequate especially for AI enabling democracy projects. Genuine European digital sovereignty requires treating data infrastructure as seriously as compute infrastructure.

1.5. EU Policy Alignment & Critique

This brief aligns with key EU policy frameworks: the European Democracy Action Plan's vision for citizen engagement; the EU AI Act's requirements for trustworthy AI (as amended by the Digital Omnibus on AI, November 2025); the European Data Strategy and Data Union Strategy's goals for data accessibility; the European Democracy Shield's emphasis on protecting democratic institutions; and Council of Europe Recommendation No. 2836 (December 2023), which requires the introduction of deliberative practices among ordinary instruments for constructing public policies.

However, we acknowledge substantial scholarly and civil society critique². Scholarly critiques note the AI Act's negotiation process has been characterised by democratic deficit, with civil society largely excluded from key decision-making despite representing affected populations. European Digital Rights (EDRi) notes the final Act omits bans on emotion recognition in potentially harmful uses such as border/migration contexts³ The Digital Omnibus shifts AI literacy from mandatory to 'encouraged,' potentially weakening capacity-building.

These critiques inform our recommendations, which aim to strengthen democratic accountability in AI deliberation implementation.

² For additional critique, see the national security exception enabling Member States to exempt AI use from the Act without EU-level definition of "national security." See ECJ judgment *La Quadrature du Net and Others v Premier ministre and Ministère de la Culture*, Case C-470/21, 30 April 2024.

³ European Digital Rights (EDRi) (2024). Available at: <https://edri.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Statement-AI-Act-migration.pdf>

2. Key Findings From Research

Drawing on D1.1's systematic review of 320+ papers, analysis of 50 platforms, stakeholder consultations, and recent scholarship (2023-2025), we identify conditions for effective AI-enabled deliberation organised around three categories: normative, institutional and technical.

2.1. Conditions for Effective AI-Enabled Deliberation

2.1.1. Normative Conditions

Transparency and explainability emerge as foundational requirements. Citizens need to understand when AI is being used, what it does and how it affects their participation. This extends beyond technical explainability to meaningful disclosure that non-expert users can comprehend, including training data sources and potential biases.

Human agency and meaningful oversight must be preserved. AI should augment rather than replace human judgment in deliberative processes. This means maintaining human moderators with genuine authority, ensuring participants can challenge AI-generated outputs and designing override mechanisms for automated decisions.

Democratic values alignment and resistance to 'technocratic bias' addresses the risk that AI systems prioritise efficiency, consensus or measurable outcomes over the messier realities of democratic disagreement, minority viewpoints and productive contestation. Commercial AI tools developed for other purposes may embed values misaligned with deliberative democracy. This encompasses tensions between commercial versus democratic values, efficiency-first approaches, developer control and over-automation risks.

Protection against 'diabolic strategies' requires AI systems capable of distinguishing legitimate grievances from manipulative rhetoric, detecting coordinated inauthentic behavior and supporting bridging communication across deep divides. Systems must function productively under polarization without either excluding authentic citizen voice or amplifying bad-faith manipulation.

Minority viewpoint preservation must be explicitly designed into AI summarization and synthesis. LLMs risk underrepresenting minority perspectives and exhibit input order bias (Zhu et al., 2025). Algorithmic fairness metrics must include specific protection for numerically small but democratically essential viewpoints.

2.1.2. Institutional Conditions

Legal compliance encompasses GDPR requirements for personal data processing, AI Act obligations for high-risk systems (noting Digital Omnibus timeline adjustments to December 2027/August 2028), and national data governance frameworks. D2.1's analysis confirms deliberation platforms processing citizen data face significant compliance obligations requiring dedicated expertise.

Organisational capacity and skills requirements are substantial. Public administrations — particularly at municipal level, which are chronically underfinanced and understaffed—need

staff capable of specifying AI requirements, evaluating vendor offerings, conducting adversarial testing and maintaining ongoing oversight. Capacity-building measures from national and European level are essential to support local administrations in reaching this ambition. The Digital Omnibus transforms the AI Act's mandatory AI literacy obligation (Article 4) for providers and deployers into a non-binding responsibility for the Commission and Member States to 'encourage' AI literacy measures.⁴ This shift from binding organizational obligation to aspirational governmental encouragement risks weakening capacity-building precisely when AI expertise becomes critical for democratic deliberation oversight.

Sustainable resource models and governance accountability remain challenging. AI-enabled deliberation requires ongoing investment in infrastructure, training, evaluation, and security and not merely one-time implementation costs. Moreover, systems must be publicly governed and open source to prevent private capture of public digital infrastructure.

2.1.3. Technical Conditions

Infrastructure readiness includes not only compute resources but also the data pipelines and standards that make AI development possible. The gap between EU investment in AI Factories (compute) and investment in AI-ready data infrastructure represents a significant asymmetry undermining digital sovereignty claims.

Interoperability and platform independence are essential for avoiding vendor lock-in and ensuring public investment produces public goods. Open APIs, standard data formats and portable architectures enable institutions to switch providers and share improvements.

Multilingual and accessibility capabilities are first and foremost democratic necessities. EU deliberation tools must function across 24 official languages.

Adversarial robustness and security must be tested before deployment. Systems require detection capabilities for coordinated inauthentic behavior, protection against manipulation of algorithmic summarization and audit trails documenting how AI decisions are made.

2.1.4. Legal and Ethical Prerequisites

GDPR compliance requires documented legal basis and Data Protection Impact Assessments for high-risk processing. Depending on implementation, deliberation systems may qualify as high-risk. A precautionary approach recommends conformity assessment, transparency obligations and human oversight requirements. Ethical review before deployment is essential. Legal compliance shall become a design prerequisite rather than a post-deployment concern.

⁴ European Commission (2025). "Proposal for a Regulation on Simplification for AI Rules (Digital Omnibus on AI)." November 19, 2025. Available at: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-omnibus-ai-regulation-proposal>

2.2. Evidence from Platform Analysis: Capabilities and Limitations

Analysis of 50 deliberation platforms reveals AI applications with demonstrated effectiveness:

- **Argument mining and structuring** helps identify claims, premises, and logical relationships within large comment volumes
- **Multilingual summarisation** enables cross-language deliberation and reduces information overload
- **Accessibility enhancement** (speech-to-text, text-to-speech, plain language conversion) broadens participation
- **Sentiment and topic analysis** provides moderators with real-time situational awareness

Persistent limitations and documented risks:

- **Bias detection and mitigation** capabilities remain immature, particularly for political and cultural contexts
- **Cross-cultural reasoning** poses challenges for AI systems trained primarily on English-language data
- **Context preservation in summarisation** often loses nuance, minority viewpoints, and conditional statements
- **No standards exist for AI-ready text** from public documents, forcing duplicated preprocessing work across organisations
- **Adversarial manipulation detection** struggles with AI-generated coordinated inauthentic behavior producing 'limitless unique comments'

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2.3. Stakeholder Needs & The 'AI Penalty'

Initial consultations with administrators, and policymakers reveal distinct priority patterns. However, recent empirical research identifies the 'AI penalty' documented by Jungherr & Rauchfleisch (2025) in a preregistered survey experiment with 1,850 representative German participants.

Key findings: participants were less willing to engage in AI-facilitated deliberation and anticipated lower deliberative quality than for human-facilitated formats. Critically, the penalty was larger among those with higher AI risk assessments, meaning AI deliberation may systematically exclude citizens most skeptical of technology, compounding existing participation biases.

Stakeholder	Priority Needs	Key Concerns
Citizens	Transparency about AI use; meaningful impact on decisions; accessible interfaces	Privacy protection; trust in AI fairness; fear of manipulation; AI penalty effect
Administrators	Workflow integration; adequate training; manageable workload; security	Resource sustainability; legal compliance; technical reliability; adversarial attacks
Policymakers	Evidence quality; democratic legitimacy; cost-effectiveness; resilience	Public acceptance; political accountability; cross-border consistency; manipulation risks

Table 1. Stakeholder needs & concerns

Implication: Human-centered design must address the AI penalty by providing parallel human-facilitated pathways for AI-skeptical participants.

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3. Policy Recommendations

The following recommendations are organised by stakeholder group. Three recommendations are marked as highest or high priority, reflecting research findings that trust, resilience, and linguistic inclusion are foundational to effective AI-enabled deliberation: R5 (Human-Centered Design) [HIGHEST PRIORITY], R8 (Design for Diabolical Times) [HIGH PRIORITY], and R4 (Linguistic Infrastructure) [HIGH PRIORITY]. Future policy briefs may reorganise recommendations based on pilot implementation experience.

3.1. For EU & National Policymakers

R1: Establish AI Deliberation Standards with Training Data Transparency & Adversarial Testing

Action: Develop EU-level technical standards for AI systems used in democratic deliberation.

Implementation: Mandate transparency and explainability requirements specific to deliberation contexts. Require training data transparency as a prerequisite for 'open source' claims. 'Open source' AI systems in deliberative contexts must disclose training data sources, curation methods, and filtering decisions—not merely model weights—to prevent open-washing that undermines transparency. Establish algorithmic auditing requirements, certification frameworks and mandatory adversarial testing ('red-teaming') before deployment. Mandate human oversight mechanisms, impact assessments for AI features and detection systems for coordinated inauthentic behavior. Require audit trails documenting how AI summarization decisions are made and minority viewpoint preservation requirements to prevent algorithmic marginalization.

Timeline: Align with AI Act implementation (2026-2028, accounting for Digital Omnibus adjustments).

R2: Invest in Sovereign Open Deliberation Infrastructure with Public Governance

Action: Fund development of open-source, publicly governed deliberation platforms, shared AI toolkits and AI-ready data infrastructure.

Implementation: Establish European AI-Ready Text Standards for public documents (schema specifications, metadata requirements, quality benchmarks). Require open infrastructure for EU-funded data labs: open-source tooling, API access for SMEs and researchers, documented reproducibility. Leverage the EU-level regulatory sandbox (operational 2028 per Digital Omnibus) for testing deliberation tools. Integrate with Horizon Europe and Digital Europe Programme funding priorities. Require public governance structures for EU-funded infrastructure with mechanisms preventing private capture.

Rationale: Public investment should produce public goods under public governance.

R3: Build Capacity & Ensure Comprehensive Accessibility

Action: Support comprehensive capacity building while ensuring accessibility across all EU languages and addressing socioeconomic barriers.

Implementation: Develop training programmes for public administrators on AI specification, evaluation, adversarial testing and oversight. Create public education initiatives on AI-enabled participation. Mandate WCAG 2.1 AA compliance as minimum standard for all deliberation platforms. Provide offline and hybrid participation options to bridge digital divides. Conduct pre-deployment equity impact assessments examining differential effects by socioeconomic status, education level, cultural background, political orientation and AI attitudes.

Rationale: Digital divides compound into AI divides. Diversity is a democratic value; AI infrastructure must reflect it while addressing broader dimensions of inequality.

R4: Invest in Linguistic Infrastructure for Democratic Participation [HIGH PRIORITY]

Action: Create dedicated investment pathways for AI-ready language infrastructure for deliberation across all EU official languages.

Implementation: Establish dedicated funding within Digital Europe or Horizon Europe for 'AI-Ready Language Infrastructure' projects. Require open licensing and reproducible pipelines as funding conditions. Coordinate cultural heritage institutions with AI developers for corpus building. Invest in efficient, locally-deployable open source language models fine-tuned for EU languages with fewer than 15 million speakers. Fully open source models suitable for on-premise hosting reduce both cost barriers and data sovereignty concerns, enabling smaller Member States and municipalities to deploy AI deliberation tools without dependence on commercial services that prioritise high-resource languages.

Rationale: European digital sovereignty is meaningful only if it serves all Europeans. Linguistic diversity is a democratic value and AI infrastructure should reflect it.

3.2. For Deliberation Practitioners

R5: Adopt Human-Centered Design Addressing the 'AI Penalty' [HIGHEST PRIORITY]

Action: Place human needs, capabilities, and trust at the centre of AI-enabled deliberation design while addressing empirical evidence of AI-induced participation barriers.

Implementation: Implement co-creation processes involving diverse stakeholder groups from project inception. Establish iterative design and evaluation cycles with rapid feedback incorporation. Prioritise user feedback loops at every stage of deployment. Balance innovation with proven methods. Start small and scale up gradually. Provide parallel human-facilitated pathways for AI-skeptical participants to address the 'AI penalty' documented by Jungherr & Rauchfleisch (2025). Resist technocratic bias by prioritising democratic values—pluralism, dissent, and deliberative quality—over efficiency metrics, speed, or consensus optimisation. AI tools should support the 'messiness' of democratic disagreement rather than streamline it away.

Rationale: Empirical evidence shows AI facilitation creates participation barriers among skeptical citizens (Section 2.3).

R6: Implement Robust Evaluation Frameworks Beyond DQI/DRI

Action: Build systematic evaluation into AI-enabled deliberation from the outset, acknowledging limitations of existing frameworks.

Implementation: Apply established deliberative quality indices (DQI, DRI) adapted for AI-enabled context. Track AI output quality metrics including accuracy, bias, context preservation, and minority viewpoint representation. Monitor user experience and trust indicators through regular surveys and behavioral analysis. Document data lineage from source to model output for auditability. Address the efficiency-legitimacy tension explicitly. For instance democratic legitimacy may require apparent 'inefficiency' (time for reflection, minority voice amplification, genuine power-sharing). Guard against technocratic bias in evaluation metrics. Avoid measuring success solely through efficiency indicators (speed, volume processed, consensus reached). Include qualitative measures of pluralism preserved, minority viewpoints surfaced, and productive contestation enabled.

Note: AI4Deliberation will attempt to contribute evaluation methodologies through its three pilot evaluation sprints.

3.3. For Technology Developers

R7: Embrace Open Standards & Interoperability

Action: Design deliberation tools for openness, portability and long-term sustainability.

Technical Standards: Open-source by default with API-first architecture. Standard data formats. Data portability and platform independence enabling institutional choice. Publish preprocessing tooling under open licenses with documentation for reproducibility.

Rationale: Open infrastructure multiplies impact so that every organisation can build on shared work rather than duplicating it.

3.4. Addressing Critical Gaps

R8: Design for Deliberation in Diabolical Times [HIGH PRIORITY]

Action: Develop AI for deliberation systems capable of actively countering conditions of deep polarization, bad-faith actors and 'diabolic strategies'—building discursive bridges and repairing democratic discourse rather than merely surviving adversarial conditions.

Implementation: Distinguish legitimate grievances from manipulative rhetoric in AI moderation—critical distinction between populist citizens (with legitimate concerns) and populist elites (manipulative power-seekers). Develop 'bridging rhetoric' capabilities enabling productive engagement across value divides without requiring factual agreement. Implement meta-consensus approaches that identify shared values beneath factual disagreements. Create multi-layered deliberative responses for populist, extremist, and denialist participation—reaching persuadable individuals while limiting elite manipulation. Design systems that preserve productive contestation rather than merely enforcing consensus.

Rationale: Contemporary European politics features diabolical challenges requiring deliberation designed for contestation not just consensus. Research shows bridging rhetoric enabled climate deniers to accept mitigation policies even while continuing to dispute anthropogenic climate change—demonstrating deliberation can proceed productively without requiring agreement on contested facts (Bächtiger & Dryzek, 2024).

R9: Establish AI Deliberation Security Standards

Action: Protect AI deliberation systems against manipulation.

Implementation: Mandate adversarial testing ('red-teaming')—systematic simulation of attacks to uncover vulnerabilities such as prompt injection, bias amplification and minority viewpoint suppression before deployment. Require detection and disclosure of synthetic/bot participation. GenAI enables 'limitless unique comments' evading detection as documented in the 2017 US regulatory manipulation.

Establish audit trails for AI summarization decisions with explicit minority viewpoint preservation requirements. Develop coordinated inauthentic behavior detection specific to deliberation contexts. Address manipulation of algorithmic moderation, gaming of summarization systems and 'deliberation washing' (using AI participation for legitimacy without genuine influence).

Timeline: Standards development concurrent with AI Act implementation.

R10: Conduct Comprehensive Equity Impact Assessments

Action: Systematically evaluate how AI deliberation affects participation across multiple dimensions of inequality.

Implementation: Pre-deployment assessment examining differential effects by socioeconomic status, education, cultural background, and AI attitudes (not merely language/disability). Address the 'AI penalty' by providing parallel human-facilitated pathways for AI-skeptical populations. Monitor for 'AI-induced participation attrition' excluding specific demographic groups. Evaluate cultural bias in AI systems that may systematically advantage certain reasoning styles or perspectives.

Rationale: Digital divides compound into AI divides with 'spill-over effects.' Legitimacy requires genuinely inclusive participation across all dimensions of inequality.

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4. Looking Ahead

4.1. Empirical Validation Roadmap

AI4Deliberation will validate these principles through rigorous empirical testing across four pilot contexts (Greece: opengov.gr legislative consultation; Italy: national deliberation; Germany: Consul-based municipal participation; International: DebateGraph cross-border policy). Three evaluation sprints (February 2026, August 2026, August 2027) will progressively test basic AI features through full deployment with comprehensive evaluation.

4.2. Future Policy Briefs

This State of Knowledge brief will be followed by evidence-based updates:

- **Policy Brief #2** (December 2026) Comparative analysis across pilots, refined recommendations)
- **Policy Brief #3** (October 2027): Consolidated recommendations with full evidence base

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GLOSSARY

Term	Definition
Adversarial testing (Red-teaming)	Structured simulation of malicious attacks on AI systems to uncover vulnerabilities before deployment. Unlike traditional testing, it targets AI-specific weaknesses including prompt injection, data poisoning, model evasion, and bias amplification. Required under EU AI Act Article 15 for high-risk systems and Article 55 for GPAI models with systemic risk.
AI-enabled deliberation	Democratic discussion processes augmented by artificial intelligence tools to enhance scale, quality, or accessibility
AI penalty	Empirically documented phenomenon where citizens are less willing to engage in AI-facilitated deliberation and anticipate lower deliberative quality, creating a new 'deliberative divide' (Jungheer & Rauchfleisch, 2025)
AI-ready text	Structured, standardised text corpora suitable for AI model training, with consistent formatting, metadata, and licensing
Bridging rhetoric	Communication capable of reaching those who don't share the speaker's perspective, enabling productive deliberation without requiring factual agreement on contested issues
Coordinated inauthentic behavior	Organized campaigns using fake identities to simulate grassroots support or opposition in democratic processes. Example: 18 million fraudulent comments (82% of submissions) submitted to US Federal Communications Commission in 2017, funded by industry groups to provide regulatory 'cover' for policy changes (New York Attorney General, 2021).
Diabolic strategies	Manipulative tactics deployed by 'clever operators' including spreading misinformation, extreme spin, and imposing their own reality through repetition without evidence (Bächtiger & Dryzek, 2024)
Digital Omnibus on AI	November 2025 EU legislative proposal amending AI Act implementation timelines and requirements
DQI / DRI	Discourse Quality Index and Deliberative Reason Index—measures of deliberative quality with acknowledged limitations (cannot assess sincerity, inadequately capture interactivity)

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Term	Definition
Open-washing	Practice of claiming 'open source' status for AI models while concealing training data sources and methodologies
Technocratic bias	Risk that AI tools prioritise efficiency, measurability, or consensus over democratic values such as pluralism, dissent, and productive contestation

Table 2. Glossary of terms

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